

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL COMMUNICATION ON HUMAN INTERACTION			Computer Science
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Mefail Tahiri	University of Tetova. North Macedonia		
Ejup Rustemi	University of Tetova. North Macedonia		
Abstract			
<p>Digital communication is simply all the media related to the digital world that allow a brand or a company to increase its availability while improving its visibility on the internet. Therefore, it is now essential for companies to use this type of communication, which is opposed to so-called traditional communication and which, in turn, is linked to conventional displays and advertising standards. This form of marketing is still used, but is slowly becoming obsolete. Currently, regardless of the age or sector of activity of the brand or company in question, digital communication is the only way to convey a modern and dynamic image and therefore, which also really makes it possible to increase its turnover over the long term as well as the number of customers.</p>			

INTRODUCTION

When do we need digital communication and through which channels do we communicate today within companies?

Digital communication is a new communication discipline .It designates all the exchanges and information transmitted via all the media offered by the digital ecosystem.

In the professional field, digital communication defines the communication strategies and actions carried out on the web with the aim of transmitting:

- messages, values,
- or even results.

These actions carried out attract the attention of target Internet users and improve the visibility of your company.

Appeared since the development of the Internet, digital communication is always in constant evolution. It follows the different changes in use and technological advances in the digital field.

Currently, to convey messages, digital communication uses a lot:

- network animation,
- or the moderation of a community.

THE DIGITAL WORLD

Often confused with digital marketing, and even if the borders are becoming more and more diluted between digital communication and digital marketing, they remain two terms not to be confused.

Indeed, while digital marketing focuses on issues of offers and user experiences on the web, digital communication focuses on the interaction between Internet users and companies.

CHANNELS OF DIGITAL COMMUNICATION

Because digital communication is a matter of objectives to be achieved and then of strategies to be implemented, depending on this, you can decide to share messages with a restricted circle of people or ensure that the information reaches as many as possible.

Do you want to attract new customers? Improve the image of your brand? Promote a whole new service?

Depending on your objectives, the appropriate digital communication channels will not be the same. Whatever the need may be, digital communication can be done through:

- social networks (main digital communication channel),
- the website,
- the blog,
- mobile app,
- or emailing.

CONCLUSION

In addition to the broadcast channel, the form chosen and then given to the messages sent is also an integral part of the digital communication strategy.

Depending on the type of information to be transmitted, but also on the targeted Internet users, the person in charge of digital communication can opt for a message taking the form:

- of a text,
- a photograph, an illustration,
- of an animation,
- or a video.

To achieve its ultimate goal, which is to attract attention and interact with Internet users, digital communication does not require a large budget to be effective, unlike traditional communication (advertising, press, events, etc.)

Digital communication is finally a great vector of opportunities to transmit information on a service / a product / an entity, but also to embellish them.

Finally, digital communication greatly facilitates reaching new customers thanks to the simple and rapid interactions it allows.

References

- Ahmad, F., Sarkar, A., (2016). Analysis of dynamic web services: Towards efficient Discovery in cloud. Malays. J. Comput. Sci. 29.
- Human-Computer Interaction: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications. Edited by the Management Association Board, Information Resources, IGI Global, Hershey.
- Illinsky, N., Steele, J., Designing Data Visualizations: Representing Informational Relationships, 2011, Sebastopol
- Kirk, A., Data Visualization: A Successful Design Process, 2012 Birmingham.
- Sears, A., Jacko, J.A. (2009). Human-Computer Interaction: Development Process. CRC Press, London.